

Interesterification Reaction of Glycerides and Their Industrial Uses (Including a discussion of India's edible oil deficits and possible remedies)[†]

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OVER a decade and half, our country has become a major importer of oils and fats instead of remaining as a country of a major exporter of oils and oil seeds in order to just meet the demand of edible and industrial requirements. We are all familiar that our per capita consumption is very low, about 5 kg compared to many developed and developing countries. An idea about the oil and fat situation in the country can be obtained from the projection of statistics as in Table 1. It may be noted that there is about 1.6 million tonnes of oil deficit, a substantial part of which is made through imports. Before the causes of shortage and their remedy are discussed, it is considered to project Table 2 to indicate the major oils of the country.

TABLE 1—DEMAND—SUPPLY PROJECTIONS OF VEGETABLE OILS (in lakh tonnes)

	1982-83	1984-85	2000 A.D.	
Demand	45.38	53.51	87.47	(Under 3.5% growth in national income)
Supply	39.38	40.00	51.54	
Gap	6.00	13.51	35.93	
Production target of vegetable oils in 6th Plan by 1984-85 (in lakh tonnes)				
Edible oils			40.75	
Non-edible oils			9.10	
Total			49.85 or 50.00	

TABLE 2—AVAILABILITY OF MAJOR INDIAN SEED OILS (in lakh tonnes)

	Actual availability 1981-82	Estimated availability by the end of 6th Plan, 1984-85 (in lakh tonnes)
Groundnut	14.12	19.40
Rape and mustard	6.45	8.20
Coconut	2.12	3.00 (+ Palm)
Cottonseed	2.24	3.50
Sesame	1.49	2.00
Linseed	1.52	1.63
Castor	0.93	1.17
Safflower	0.48	0.86
Soyabean	0.70	1.55
Nigerseed	0.29	0.60
Sunflower	0.57	1.64

The main causes of shortage are understandable from Table 3. For several years, a number of remedial measures have been conceived and implemented or being given serious considerations for working out the suggested measures. There are two main remedial measures, (i) increased production of oil seeds through irrigation, using high yielding varieties, and using other agricultural inputs, and (ii) evolving new technologies and/or improvised technologies besides concentrating on finding out alternative sources of oil seeds. Table 4 just gives the remedial measure as suggested.

TABLE 3—CAUSES OF SHORTAGE OF OIL SEEDS AND OILS

1. Low productivity (acrage yield) due to
 - (a) Use of marginal or near marginal lands,
 - (b) Lack of proper irrigation,
 - (c) Lack of adequate use of agricultural inputs, namely fertilisers, good quality seeds, plant protection materials.
2. Low acreage use for cultivation.
3. Reluctancy on the part of farmers to invest for oilseeds because of high risk of crop failure
4. Low priority towards development oilseed crops from the centre and the state.
5. Adequate attention has not been paid to utilise full potential of non-traditional oils and tap new sources of oil.
6. Lack of co-ordination between research findings and extension services.

TABLE 4—REMEDIES OF SHORTAGE OF OILS AND FATS

1. Increasing the production of major oilseeds by improving cultivation practices and using improved variety of oilseeds.
2. Utilisation of the full potential of minor oilseeds of tree origin, by-product sources including marine and other existing less known sources.
3. Tapping entirely new sources of oilseeds.
4. Developing process technology.

While considerable progress is made on the agricultural aspect of oil seeds, much headway has been made also in finding out the new oils as indicated in

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the Tables 5-7. This definitely points out that there are resources of by-products and other minor oils which can contribute significantly to increase our vegetable oils production for edible and industrial consumptions.

As regards evolving technologies, no doubt some advancement has been made in our refineries. As for example, the refining of high FFA oils, 20 percent and above, is now done by high vacuum steam stripping and by miscella refining instead of the traditional alkali refining process that is only suitable for low FFA oils.

About eighty percent of our oils is used for edible purpose as cooking oil and in producing vanaspati and bakery fat. Vanaspati is the largest processed food fat (1 million tonnes) and consumes 20 percent of our edible oils. Vanaspati characteristics and the oils used at present for the production of vanaspati are shown in Tables 8 and 9.

TABLE 5—AVAILABILITY OF LESS KNOWN/NON-TRADITIONAL OILS AND FATS IN INDIA (in thousand tonnes)

	Availability	
	Potential	Actual
Rice bran	600	150
Mowrah	171	25
Sal	688	25
Kokum	0.8	0.2
Dhupa	1.0	0.4
Mango	30	0.15

TABLE 6—MINOR INDIAN SEED OILS OF COMMERCIAL IMPORTANCE

	Oil potential tonnes
Jute seed	8000
Tobacco seed	6000
Water melon	5600
Wild castor	350
Maize germ	20384

TABLE 7—AVAILABILITY OF OTHER BY-PRODUCT OILS (in thousand tonnes)

	Oil potential
Rubber seed	40
Silkworm pupae	14
Marine oils	50

TABLE 8—DEFINITION AND CHARACTERISTICS OF VANASPATI
Vanaspati is defined as a blend of deacidified, bleached, subjected to process of modification including partial hydrogenation and deodorised edible vegetable oils with specified quantity of refined vegetable oil(s) meant for human consumption.

Physical appearance :	Grainy consistency, pale cream to white in colour
Slip point :	33-41°
Iodine value :	65-72
Fatty acids (% w/w) :	
	Saturates 30-35
	Oleic 50-55
	Linoleic 8-10
	Trans 35-40

In our country vegetable oils are hydrogenated for several decades to produce vanaspati, a product which is used as substitute of *Ghee*. As an alternative to the hydrogenation process another very useful process based on interesterification reaction of glycerides has been developed. The process is in commercial practice, in some of the developed countries to produce plastic fat products from liquid oils for use as food fats in the form of margarines and also shortenings. In the past few years some basic studies on the nutritional aspects of *trans*-unsaturated fatty acids point out that these acids invariably formed during the hydrogenation reaction are atherogenic (responsible for arterial disease) and linoleic acid, the essential fatty acid, also becomes considerably *trans*-isomeric and can not act as essential fatty acid. Some of those allegations are shown in Table 10.

TABLE 9—VEGETABLE OILS USED AT PRESENT IN INDIA FOR VANASPATI PRODUCTION (%)

Soybean	—	50-60
Rice bran	—	30-60
Palm	—	20-30
Sesame	—	5
Mowrah	—	10-15
Sal	—	5-10

Other potential oils for Vanaspati production :
Palm olein and Palm stearin.

TABLE 10—SHORTCOMINGS OF VANASPATI

1. High *trans* and positional isomeric unsaturated fatty acids.

Effects :

- (i) Increase serum lipid and cholesterol levels in man.
- (ii) Inhibit chain elongation of linoleate to arachidonate.

2. Low PUFA content.

Effect :

- (i) Insufficient for lowering or maintaining serum cholesterol or lipids in case of hypercholesterolemia.
- (ii) Not adequate for incorporation into arachidonic acid, a precursor of prostaglandin synthesis.

In view of these observations, the interesterification process is gaining preference to the hydrogenation process in producing similar kinds of fat products. This process technology has not yet been commercially adopted as the Government of India has not yet cleared this process formally. However, at a recent meeting of the Central Committee of Food Standards the definition of vanaspati has been changed to include the process of interesterification and it is being hoped that the formal clearance will be given without any further delay. We have been working on the interesterification process for about two decades to evolve standard conditions of this process so that a number of liquid oils as such or mixtures can be converted to vanaspati like fats. The interesterification process is based primarily on two kinds of ester-ester interchange

reactions, i.e. random and directed reaction. The reaction is known as random because natural oils become so oriented in their glyceride pattern forming composition of glyceride which is similar to the composition that one can obtain by esterifying glycerol with a mixture of fatty acids. In fact, all the theoretically possible glycerides are formed as a result of random reaction. If this random reaction is continued at low temperatures at which some of the glycerides can be made to crystallise out, a new kind of products are formed in which some specific triglycerides are more predominant when the process is called the direct interesterification process. Chart 1 shows the chemistry of the interesterification reactions. The ester-ester interchange reaction has been exploited to the maximum in modifying the composition and properties of oils and fats. Chart 2 indicates how this reaction is conducted.

Alcoholysis

Acidolysis

Ester-ester interchange

Chart 1. Interesterification reactions of glycerides.

Chart 2. Interesterification process.

As pointed out earlier that vanaspati of hydrogenated type and margarine fat bases can be made from liquid oils individually or in combination by the interesterification process. We became interested in the utilisation of some tree borne seed fats, by product oils and some imported oils and fats in making fat products simulating vanaspati and also for use in making margarine.

Among the seed fats, sal and mowrah are unique in their fatty acid and triglyceride composition and these seed fats can be interesterified with by-product oils, like cottonseed and rice bran to give products similar to vanaspati. Similarly, sal fat can be effectively interesterified with sunflower oil which is expected to become a major edible oil in near future. Table 11 will give clear indication how the liquid oils can be converted to fat products of vanaspati consistency without hydrogenation.

For the past 6-7 years, we are importing palm oil and palmolein for vanaspati production by hydrogenation in combination with other liquid oils, like soyabean, rice bran and rapeseed. The use of palm oil and palmolein in vanaspati is limited to between 20 and 30 percent beyond which vanaspati tends to show a distinct phase separation. From economic point of view, the more use of palm oil and palmolein would have been preferred to the other liquid oils used. Much importance is, therefore, now being directed to investigate more critically the suitability of the interesterification process for making vanaspati like fats using each fat exclusively between 50 and 80 percent when blended with the liquid oils that are used for vanaspati production by hydrogenation. Besides palm and palmolein, it is also known that palm stearin, another important fraction of palm oil, is also gaining much importance in view of its physicochemical characteristics for making once again vanaspati production.

Tables 12-15 give an indication about the condition of interesterification reaction and the physicochemical characteristics of the interesterified products. It can be concluded that palm oil and its fractions can be utilised in much better way in more enhanced quantity between 50 and 100 percent in making vanaspati without hydrogenation.

TABLE 11—CHARACTERISTICS OF THE INTERESTERIFIED PRODUCTS OBTAINED FROM BLENDS OF SAL OIL/MOWRAH OIL WITH LIQUID OILS*

Interesterified fat	Slip point °C	Glyceride composition				Solid fat index at °C				
		S _s	S ₁ U	SU _s	U _s	20	25	30	35	40
Sal+Cottonseed										
(3 : 7, w/w) Randomised	35	8.4	18.6	30.6	42.4	3.9	5.4	8.5	1.4	—
(1 : 1, w/w) Randomised	41	9.9	35.8	35.7	18.6	14.5	12.3	8.0	5.9	2.8
Sal+Sunflower										
(1 : 1, w/w) Randomised	38	5.3	22.5	46.1	28.1	13.3	9.2	6.4	4.6	3.0
Sal+Rice bran										
(1 : 1, w/w) Randomised	35.5	7.8	29.3	53.9	19.0	11.7	7.4	5.0	2.4	—
Directed 15 ^o /6 h	37.5	10.3	29.4	25.0	35.3	12.5	11.0	8.9	6.3	3.9
Mowrah+Rice bran										
(1 : 1, w/w) Directed 15 ^o /48 h	38	9.4	29.5	22.8	28.3	17.4	12.7	9.4	6.8	3.1

* S. Adhikari, J. Dasgupta, D. K. Bhattacharyya and M. M. Chakrabarty, *Fette, Seifen. Anstrichm.*, 1981, 83, 262 ; 1982, 84, 146.

TABLE 12—GLYCERIDE COMPOSITION OF INTERESTERIFIED PRODUCTS OBTAINED FROM PALM OIL AND PALMOLEIN IN COMBINATION WITH LIQUID OILS*

Fat products	Slip point °C	Glyceride composition, mol			
		S ₃	S ₂ U	SU ₂	U ₃
Palm + Cotton seed (7 : 3), D.I. 15°/1 h	39	8.0	28.1	32.2	31.7
Palm + Rice bran (7 : 3), D.I. 15°/1 h	36	6.0	26.0	39.8	28.2
Palm + Mowrah (7 : 3), D.I. 15°/4 h	36	9.1	31.2	37.6	22.1
Palm + Soyabean (7 : 3), D.I. 15°/4 h	36	6.0	23.1	39.9	31.0
Palm + Rapeseed (8 : 2), D.I. 15°/5 h	36	6.0	29.0	44.0	21.0
Palmolein D.I. 15°/4h	37	9.5	33.9	39.1	17.1
Palmolein + Mowrah (6 : 4), Randomised	37	8.6	32.6	41.3	17.5

* D. K. Bhattacharyya, J. Dasgupta and K. Banerjee, Paper presented at the International Conference on 'Palm Oil Product Technology in the Eighties', June, 1981, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.

TABLE 13—CHARACTERISTICS OF INTERESTERIFIED FATS*

Fat product	Slip point °C	Iodine value	Solid fat index at °C			
			20	25	30	37
Palm + Cotton seed (7 : 3), 15°/1 h	39	67.3	16.0	12.0	9.3	5.1
Palm + Rice bran (7 : 3), 15°/1 h	36	71.0	14.0	10.1	7.6	3.4
Palm + Mowrah (7 : 3), 15°/1 h	36	63.0	17.7	16.5	15.2	5.3
Palm + Soyabean (7 : 3), 15°/4 h	36	70.2	6.7	6.0	4.3	-
Palm + Rapeseed (8 : 2), 4°/5 h	36	72.4	16.2	11.5	8.3	1.1

*Ref. as in Table 12.

TABLE 14—CHARACTERISTICS OF PALM OIL AND PALMOLEIN BASED INTERESTERIFIED FATS*

Fat product	Slip point °C	Iodine value	Solid fat index at °C			
			20	25	30	37
Palmolein, D.I. 15°/4 h	37	59.0	13.6	10.6	7.2	-
Palmolein + Sal (9 : 1), Randomised	35	59.5	27.2	20.1	15.3	3.2
D.I. 15°/2 h	37	59.5	30.1	22.8	16.6	4.6
Palmolein + Mowrah (6 : 5), Randomised	37	61.2	17.5	16.1	14.3	5.1
Palm + Cotton seed + Sal (5 : 3 : 2), Randomised	38	70.4	28.5	21.7	15.2	4.5
Palm + Rice bran + Sal (5 : 3 : 2), Randomised	38	67.3	17.1	12.0	9.2	4.1

*Ref. as in Table 12.

TABLE 15—CHARACTERISTICS OF INTERESTERIFIED FATS FROM BLENDS OF PALM STEARIN AND LIQUID OILS*

Fat product	Slip point °C	Iodine value	Solid fat index at °C			
			20	25	30	37
Palm stearin (I) + Rice bran (1 : 1), 15°/2 h	36	70.9	13.1	10.6	7.4	-
Palm stearin (I) + Cotton seed (1 : 1), 15°/2 h	37	76.1	12.1	10.9	8.5	1.5
Palm stearin + Rapeseed (4 : 6), Randomised	35	84.8	9.5	6.6	4.6	-
Palm stearin (II) + Soyabean (4 : 6), Randomised	36	73.8	5.4	3.1	2.3	-

*Ref. as in Table 12

The investigation on nutritional quality of the interesterified fat products reveal that the interesterified fats are equivalent to hydrogenated vanaspati with respect to the coefficient of digestibility, triglyceride and cholesterol level. Food efficiency and the growth rate of rats fed vanaspati and two interesterified fat products are given in Tables 16-17. Total lipid and lipid composition of plasma and liver lipids are included in Tables 18 and 19.

TABLE 16—FOOD EFFICIENCY RATIOS OF DIETS CONTAINING VANASPATI (I) vs INTERESTERIFIED PALMOLEIN (II) AT 10% LEVEL, AND VANASPATI (III) vs INTERESTERIFIED PALM STEARIN + RICE BRAN (IV) AT 20% LEVEL

Week	Food efficiency ratio			
	10% level		20% level	
	I	II	III	IV
1	0.479	0.426	0.405	0.416
2	0.439	0.409	0.392	0.366
3	0.409	0.393	0.370	0.342
4	0.384	0.376	0.354	0.324
5	0.364	0.362	0.332	0.310
6	0.344	0.350	0.322	0.300
7	0.329	0.332	0.305	0.290
8	0.318	0.323	0.290	0.282
9	0.300	0.305	0.275	0.269
10	0.281	0.282	0.254	0.254
11	0.256	0.257	0.236	0.236
12	0.235	0.237	0.229	0.213

TABLE 17—MEAN BODY WEIGHT OF DIETS, VANASPATI (I) vs INTERESTERIFIED PALMOLEIN (II) AT 10% LEVEL, AND VANASPATI (III) vs INTERESTERIFIED PALM STEARIN + RICE BRAN (IV) AT 20% LEVEL

Week	Mean body weight gain, g			
	10% level		20% level	
	I	II	III	IV
1	32	25.1	23.3	23.9
2	62.8	58.8	35.2	39.0
3	92.1	86.5	55.0	60.3
4	117.1	111.5	65.8	74.0
5	140.4	137.0	103.1	108.4
6	168.0	161.0	129.5	132.1
7	181.1	180.0	153.3	147.8
8	201.6	201.8	177.5	173.4
9	214.1	214.6	188.3	194.0
10	223.8	221.4	191.0	206.5
11	225.4	222.2	201.6	210.0
12	225.7	225.3	216.5	209.3

In fact in case of interesterified fats the level of triglyceride and free cholesterol is generally always lower than that of vanaspati in the plasma of rats in experimental animals (Tables 18,19) and this observation suggests that the interesterified fats are hypocholesterolemic and on the basis of the findings, can be recommended as better fats than vanaspati.

One of the important points in the interesterification reaction of glycerides using chemical catalysts is that the fatty acids distribution is non-specific and makes this catalytic interesterification process less suitable for making fat products of particular specific glycerides, such as substitutes of cocoa butter. Cocoa butter, as it is known, contains particular types of glycerides in high quantity

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TABLE 18—LIPID COMPOSITION OF PLASMA AND LIVER LIPIDS OF RATS FED 10 FAT (VANASPATI AND INTERESTERIFIED PALMOLEIN)*

Test fat		Total lipid	Phospholipid	Triglyceride	Total cholesterol	Cholesterol ester
Vanaspati	Plasma (mg/100 ml)	274.8±6.6	104.8±4.8	59.8±6.1	47.5±7.6	18.2±2.2
	Liver (mg/g)	39.2±2.6	28.0±1.0	1.9±0.3	0.55±0.06	0.11±0.02
	Plasma (mg/100 ml)	272.8±6.0	111.3±12.3	55.0±2.6	47.9±5.0	18.0±2.0
Interesterified palm olein	Liver (mg/g)	38.3±2.1	30.6±2.0	2.4±0.4	0.5±0.2	0.1±0.01

*D. K. Bhattacharyya, A. C. Bhattacharyya, R. Basu and S. Majumder, Paper presented at the 26th World Congress of the International Society for Fat Research, October 4-7, 1983, Budapest, Proceedings in the press.

TABLE 19—LIPID COMPOSITION OF PLASMA, LIVER AND ERYTHROCYTE MEMBRANE OF RATS FED 20 DIET*

Test fat		Total lipid	Phospholipid	Triglyceride	Total cholesterol	Cholesterol ester
Vanaspati	Plasma (mg/100 ml)	307.6±16.9	61.9±4.4	65.2±10.7	51.5±4.3	22.7±0.5
	Liver (mg/g)	41.1±4.2	15.3±0.4	0.9±0.0	4.2±0.15	0.37±0.06
	Membrane (mg/100 ml RBC)	—	85.8±7.0	—	72.1±8.0	—
Interesterified palm stearin + rice bran oil	Plasma (mg/100 ml)	405.2±13.3	124.7±4.2	81.2±6.0	78.2±6.8	38.1±3.3
	Liver (mg/g)	42.1±0.5	23.4±1.5	1.4±0.14	5.1±0.3	0.33±0.03
	Membrane (mg/100 ml RDC)	—	95.8±6.5	—	59.1±2.2	—

*Ref. as in Table 18.

between 75 and 85 percent and, therefore, has sharp melting characteristics which are utilised in chocolate preparations. In order to have glycerides of specific structures from natural oils or their fractions, enzyme catalysts have been found to give more specific interesterification reaction. The first enzymatic interesterification reaction has been reported by Macrae who was able to obtain some microorganisms that contain specific enzyme systems. The sources of microbial lipases are *Candida cylindracea*, *Geotrichum candidum*, *Rhizopus delemar* and *Aspergillus niger*. A few examples of the enzymatic interesterification reactions are given in the Tables 20-23.

TABLE 20—INTERESTERIFICATION OF A MIXTURE OF OLIVE OIL, STEARIC ACID AND LINOLEIC ACID USING *Geotrichum candidum* LIPASE AS CATALYST*

Fatty acid	Amount in olive oil %	Amount in interesterified triglyceride %
16 : 0	11.6	11.5
16 : 1	0.8	0.5
18 : 0	3.6	4.5
18 : 1	72.8	64.8
18 : 2	10.6	18.3
20 : 1	0.6	0.4

*A. R. Macrae, *J. An. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 291.

TABLE 21—INTERESTERIFICATION OF A 1 : 1 MIXTURE OF COCONUT OIL AND OLIVE OIL *Candida cylindracea* LIPASE*

Triglyceride carbon no. (excluding glycerol residue)	Composition of triglyceride interesterified oils		
	Starting mixture wt %	With alkali metal catalyst wt %	With <i>C. cylindracea</i> lipase catalyst wt %
26	0.1	0.1	0.3
28	0.3	0.2	0.5
30	1.1	0.5	0.7
32	5.0	1.4	2.1
34	6.7	2.1	2.1
36	8.4	4.2	4.0
38	7.6	6.7	6.5
40	4.5	7.2	6.6
42	3.4	13.1	12.6
44	1.9	11.6	11.4
46	1.2	11.6	11.7
48	1.0	17.4	18.0
50	4.7	6.8	7.4
52	21.2	7.4	7.2
54	31.8	9.3	8.4
56	1.0	0.4	0.5

* Ref. as in Table 20.

TABLE 22—INTERESTERIFICATION OF A MIXTURE OF OLIVE OIL AND STEARIC ACID USING *Rhizopus delemar* LIPASE*

Fatty acid	Amount in olive oil			Amount in interesterified triglycerides		
	Total TG %	2-position %	land 3-positions %	Total TG %	2-position %	land 3-positions %
16 : 0	16.6	3.5	23.2	13.7	3.2	18.9
16 : 1	1.8	1.3	2.0	1.6	1.6	1.6
18 : 0	2.0	1.0	2.5	15.6	0.7	23.0
18 : 1	66.8	72.0	64.2	56.6	72.2	48.8
18 : 2	12.8	22.2	8.1	12.6	22.3	7.7

* Ref. as in Table 20.

The ester-ester interchange reaction involving the normal catalyst system has enormous scope of utilisation in making edible fat products from a variety of liquid oils without hydrogenation. Some of the recent work have been highlighted. It can be stated that the definition of vanaspati being changed which no longer should be produced

by hydrogenation process alone, the interesterification process will now become commercial. From the point of view of cost, this process has also some advantage as tentative cost calculations indicate that the process is much cheaper as long as it is based on simple random interesterification reaction. This process will help solving many problems associated with the use of palm oil and other less known oils.

TABLE 23—INTERESTERIFICATION OF A MIXTURE OF PALM MIDFRACTION AND STEARIC ACID USING *Aspergillus niger* LIPASE AS CATALYST*

Fatty acid	Amount in triglyceride	
	Palm midfraction %	Intesterified product %
14 : 0	0.7	0.7
16 : 0	57.0	37.0
18 : 0	6.0	28.9
18 : 1	31.8	30.2
18 : 2	3.6	3.5
20 : 0	0.2	0.2
Triglyceride species**		
SSS	5	13
POP	58	19
POSt	13	32
StOSt	2	13
SSO	7	2
SLnS	9	7
SOO	4	11
Others	2	3

* Ref. as in Table 20.

** S=Saturated fatty acid group, P=Palmitate, St=Stearate, O=Oleate, Ln=Linoleate.

In fact, a number of tailor-made fats can be made that can be used as specific fats for bakery and for making margarine and halvarine (butter substitutes) of superior nutritional quality. In fact, margarine of varying polyunsaturated fatty acid (PUFA) level can be much better produced by the interesterification process.

The enzymatic interesterification process although needs much more investigation, has already shown unique advantages over the conventional chemical catalyst process and will be in no distant future a commercial proposition to produce useful glyceride mixtures which cannot be obtained by conventional chemical interesterification process.

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